

D7.4 Report on Participation and Organisation of Events

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: IMPLEMENTING GENDER EQUALITY PLANS TO UNLOCK RESEARCH POTENTIAL OF RPOS AND RFOS IN EUROPE

Grant Agreement n°: 101006416

Document Version

Version	Date	Comments / Changes	Author/ Reviewer
0.1	13 July 2023	Draft version sent to the project consortium and the Steering Committee for review	Carolina Tavares, Gisela Nascimento (FRCT)
0.2	17 July 2023	Draft version reviewed by Coordinator and partners	All partners
1.0	27 July 2023	Final version to be submitted after inclusion of comments from the project consortium and the Steering Committee	Carolina Tavares, Gisela Nascimento (FRCT)

Document Information

Project Acronym	ATHENA
Project Title	Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe
Project Number	101006416
Instrument	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans
Project Start Date	01/02/2021
Project Duration	48 months
Work Package	WP7
Task	Task 7.5 Participation and organization of events and connection/synergies with similar initiatives
Deliverable	D7.4 Report on Participation and Organisation of Events
Due Date	31/07/2023
Submission Date	27/07/2023
Dissemination Level¹	Public
Deliverable Responsible	PP10 FRCT - Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (Açores, Portugal)
Version	1.0

¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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gender equality to unlock
research potential

Status	Final
Author(s)	Carolina Tavares, Gisela Nascimento, FRCT Contributors: All partners
Reviewers	Steering Committee

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Executive Summary

Given their significance in highlighting ATHENA's contributions to gender equality in research, the project's dissemination and communication activities are a crucial component of its overall design.

The project has established a comprehensive and thorough dissemination strategy that has been carried out through a series of practical measures from the very beginning in order to:

- Increase interest in the ATHENA project;
- Increase engagement and encourage target group participation in project activities;
- Promote sustainability initiatives and ATHENA's best practices when the project is finished.

Over the past few months, the Covid-19 pandemic's exceptional worldwide restrictions have loosened up, making it possible for the partners to plan events and activities both offline and online. In this regard, the current deliverable summarises the progress on the Task 7.5 on organisation of and participation in offline and online events for dissemination purposes by the ATHENA partners from February 2021 to June 2023 (M1-M30).

This report uses the actions done by the Consortium Members as concrete examples of how the dissemination event strategy's goals might be implemented. It places strong emphasis on the organisation and participation of events within the ATHENA project, specifically targeting the creation of synergies with other projects and organisations. These events serve as valuable platforms for partners to showcase ATHENA, exchange knowledge, and foster collaborations. The report also showcases networking activities undertaken by Consortium Members, as well as additional actions taken to promote the project and its scope, such as videos, interviews, and other events.

The present deliverable is the second of three versions of the Report on Participation and Organisation of Events, delivered at M30. The last version will be prepared at the end of the project, at M48.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The deliverable presents the objectives and activities implemented to disseminate ATHENA outputs, in order to ensure the best exploitation of its results. It presents the progress and results of the ATHENA dissemination for the period M1-M30 (February 2021 – July 2023) by showing external events/conferences and joint activities/experience-sharing meetings in collaboration with other H2020 projects.

Deliverable 7.4 also analyses ATHENA dissemination strategy progress and suggests next steps to improve the dissemination action plan ensuring a maximum project visibility.

1.2 Target and Audience

The document is intended for both internal and external readers. Its dissemination level is Public. The document could be used for dissemination managers of ongoing and future projects, willing to explore ATHENA strategy and its dissemination approach and capitalise on it.

This report's goal is also to help project partners further develop their individual and collaborative activities, as well as to identify any needs to re-adjust the dissemination strategy towards the participation in and organisation of events.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured into the following sections:

- Section 1 introduces the purpose and scope of the report, as well as its target audience.
- Section 2 describes dissemination project activities (conferences, webinars, workshops and symposiums) developed during February 2021 and July 2023 (M1-M30), as well as their outreach.
- Section 3 presents general considerations as well as an evaluation of the implemented dissemination strategy in this period.

2. Dissemination Activities

In this section of the report, dissemination project activities developed during February 2021 and July 2023 are covered in detail. ATHENA partners proactive approach so far has laid good groundwork for ensuring impactful dissemination.

The dissemination activities related to participation in and organisation of events are as follows:

- Conferences
- Webinars
- Symposiums
- Debates
- Other events

2.1 Conferences

As a dissemination tool, conferences allow ATHENA project partners to showcase ATHENA project and its results. The consortium has reached a good number of conference appearances in the first 30 months of the project. Consortium representatives have networked and engaged with stakeholders, as well as presented the core objectives of ATHENA and helped promote awareness around the matter of gender equality in research.

Below is a list of those attended by partners:

Conference “Academy of 21st century - a road to inclusion in research and innovation”

Date: October 3rd, 2022 Location: Bratislava, Slovakia Partner: UVSK SAV Organiser: Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information
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The Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information hosted the Conference “Academy of the 21st century – the way to inclusion in research and innovation”. The aim of the event was to shed light on the current topic of gender equality as a policy of equal opportunities and full use of talents in science. It posed an opportunity to open the topic of gender equality in

research and innovation to a wider public, as well as to discuss optimal conditions in the academic environment of the 21st century.

Gabriel Bianchi and Miroslava Šudila Žilinská were able to exhibit the ATHENA project within presentations on the current state of gender equality inclusion in the ecosystem of Slovak science and the European strategy for gender equality and the implementation possibilities it brings, for which certain European H2020 projects of Slovak research performing institution were selected. The civic associations Aj Ty v IT, RISOTO and FEMALE ALGORITHM inspired the audience with successful examples from the business environment, whilst the association I Live Science participated in the preparation of the conference on gender equality. The conference also helped promote synergies between sister projects (CHANGE, Equal4Europe and GENDERACTION). The civic association I Live Science also participated in the preparation of the conference on gender equality.

Figure 1: Gabriel Bianchi's presentation at the Conference "Academy of 21st century - a road to inclusion in research and innovation"

International Science Conference Social Processes and Personality

Date: September 5th-7th, 2022
 Location: Stara Lesna, Slovakia
 Partner: UVSK SAV
 Organiser: Institute of Experimental Psychology of the Centre of Social and Psychological Sciences SAS

The 2022 Conference of Social Processes and Personality was open to research topics such as the transparency of psychological research, psychological connections between unfounded beliefs and current social phenomena, data sharing and open source, amongst many others. Its audience consisted of people within Slovak and Czech organisations that work in the various fields of psychology presented.

The ATHENA Project, within this conference, was presented by Gabriel Bianchi and Miroslava Šudila Žilinská, in a poster with the theme “Gender audit in SAS: case study”. Since March 2021, a research team from the Institute for Research in Social Communication SAS has been conducting a gender audit at the Academy, intending to gain a deeper understanding of the current state of gender issues. Their presentation showed the first version of the Gender Equality Plan SAS, as well as its preliminary results and the action plan that was designed to eliminate inequalities.

Final Conference of the National Project Gender Equality in the Workplace

Date: November 10th, 2022
Location: Bratislava, Slovakia
Partner: UVSK SAV
Organiser: Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic

The aim of the Final Conference of the National Project Gender Equality in the Workplace was to present the concept, proposals and ideas that arose during the implementation of the project, and which represent the basis for systemic measures in this area. The conference included a panel discussion with representatives of employers and institutions who have experience in implementing equal opportunities policy in the workplace, in which Gabriel Bianchi mentioned the ATHENA Project, during a debate on the advantages and pitfalls of applying equal opportunities.

“Women in Diplomacy” Conference

Date: November 9th, 2022
Location: Bratislava, Slovakia
Partner: UVSK SAV
Organiser: Slovak Foreign Policy Association together with the Ministry of Foreign and European Affairs of the Slovak Republic

Figure 2: Women in Diplomacy Conference Poster

The “Women in Diplomacy” Conference provided a space for evaluating the progress in inclusion and diversity in Slovak diplomacy. It mapped sociocultural, economic, and institutional barriers, analysed their impact on the current position of women and proposed practical solutions for increasing inclusion and diversity in this area.

The conference also sent an important message on the need for inclusion and diversity in institutions, during a debate about the Representation and position of women in foreign policy and diplomacy today, the ATHENA Project was presented by Gabriel Bianchi.

Community Psychology in Slovakia Conference 2021

Date: November 29th, 2021
Location: Online
Partner: UVSK SAV
Organiser: Comenius University

The goal of the Community Psychology in Slovakia Conference and Workshop was to provide a space for both researchers and practitioners from various areas of the psychology community in Europe to meet, present their work and research, inspire each other, and enjoy socializing together.

Miroslava Žilinská, Barbora Holubová, and Gabriel Bianchi presented “Gender equality in research institutions: A case study from the Slovak Academy of Sciences”, where they mentioned the work that has been carried out in the ATHENA Project.

Figure 3: UVSK SAS's presentation of the ATHENA Project

2nd International Interdisciplinary Scientific Conference, "(In)equality. Faces of Modern Europe"

Date: November 21st, 2021

Location: Online and in-person and Wroclaw, Poland

Partner: UJK

Organiser: Willy Brandt Centre for German and European Studies, Wroclaw University

The 2nd International Interdisciplinary Scientific Conference, entitled "(In)equality. Faces of Modern Europe" was organized by the IDE Academic Circle and the Willy Brandt Centre for German and European Studies of the University of Wroclaw.

The subject matter of the conference arose from the need to understand the phenomena and processes taking place in contemporary Europe. The goal of this conference was to promote young scientific talents (students and PhD students), and to propagate the idea of interdisciplinary research. This event posed an opportunity for spread the current research, including the ATHENA Project's results at UJK, which were presented by Ana Kaminska and Joanna Rudawska.

Conference "Scientific Excellence Has no Gender"

Date: February 10th, 2022
Location: Online
Partner: UJK
Organiser: Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań

The conference "Scientific Excellence Has No Gender" addressed authorities within scientific and research units, as well as representatives of the Poland Ministry of Education and Science, institutions financing science and promoting science and research in Poland.

The objective of the conference was to draw attention to the problem of inequality between women and men in various aspects of science, including the problems of young parents (mainly women) or people taking care of dependent persons practicing science. The conference was an event inaugurating a long-term Adam Mickiewicz University programme under the same slogan, the aim of which will be to counteract gender inequality in Polish science.

In this conference, Ana Kaminska was able to present the ATHENA Project during a moderated discussion on the situation of women and men in Polish science.

Conference "Gender studies and activism 2022 (re-/de-/?-? institutionalization in changing realities)"

Date: November 24th, 2022
Location: Online and in-person in Vilnius
Partner: UJK
Organiser: Vilnius University

Several gender scholars and experts gathered at the Vilnius University (on site and remotely) to discuss the perspectives of gender related issues. Three plenary sessions were devoted to gender studies in Lithuania, intersectionality and changing masculinity.

Ana Kaminska presented the ATHENA Project during the parallel sessions, aimed at hearing the presentations from members within the community of practice.

International Conference on Gender Equality: Global Challenges and Perspectives

Date: May 12th, 2022
Location: Bucharest
Partner: UB
Organiser: Dimitrie Cantemir Christian University, Institute of Social and Gender Studies

The “Gender Equality: Global Challenges and Perspectives” Conference, organized by the Institute for the Social Study of Gender, is a major cultural and social event held at Dimitrie Cantemir University in Bucharest.

In 2022, participants from over 30 countries around the world brought into attention a globalized attitude towards gender representations, diversity, equality, and inclusion in social and pluralist contexts, that covered both the social and cultural aspects of societies, in order to open new directions for future research.

The ATHENA Project, in this conference, was disseminated by Laura Grünberg, within a session called “The Institutionalization and Professionalization of Gender/Equal Opportunities Expertise in Romania”, where the speaker presented the topic “How to Make (or Not to Make) Gender Equality in Higher Education Work.”

National Conference on the Equality of Women and Men in Academic and Scientific Organizations – Good Practices, Challenges and Perspectives

Date: December 15th, 2022
Location: Sofia
Partner: URAK
Organiser: SPEAR Project

The aim of the National Conference, held on the theme of good practices, challenges and perspectives on the equality between men and women in academic and scientific organizations, was to bring together experts working in the field of equality between women and men and researchers with an interest in the field.

Experts in the field presented Equality Plans and good European practices in the implementation of monitoring tools.

Within a discussion panel, Daniel Pavlov disseminated the ATHENA Project with a presentation on the Plan for Observance of Equality between women and men in science at the University of Ruse under the Horizon 2020 Program.

National Conference for Women Harassment Under Project "WEGO! 3"

Date: March 24th, 2023
Location: Bulgaria
Partner: URAK
Organiser: URAK and project WEGO! 3

The National Conference for Women Harassment under the WEGO! 3 Project was held in connection with the 2-year anniversary of the signing of the Territorial Protocol in support of the economic empowerment of women who have experienced violence from the intimate partner.

Diana Antonova disseminated the ATHENA Project in this event within a presentation on the Plan for Observance of Equality between women and men in science at the University of Ruse under the Horizon 2020 Programme.

SPEAR Final Conference

Date: March 1st, 2023
Location: Copenhagen
Partner: FRCT, CE
Organiser: SPEAR Project

SPEAR's final conference set out to place Gender Equality Projects in the context of the future of (gender) equality, inclusivity and democratic values in European Academia, through the lenses of practices, prerequisites, pushback and prospectives.

Within this conference, the ATHENA project was presented by Carolina Bettencourt, FRCT and Marlene Santacruz, CE, within "A kaleidoscope of sister projects and initiatives and explorative networking", a group dynamic session, together with a conjoined total of 26 sister gender projects and initiatives that presented their impact and invited participants to engage.

Figure 4: ATHENA project dissemination through FRCT and CE members

Conference: Natália Correia, a Woman Ahead of Her Time

Date: March 10th, 2022
Location: Ponta Delgada
Partner: FRCT
Organiser: Azorean Regional Directorate for the Promotion of Equality and Social Inclusion

The Vice-Presidency of the Regional Government of the Azores, through the Regional Directorate for the Promotion of Equality and Social Inclusion promoted, on the International Women’s day, a commemorative conference in the Public Library and Archive of Ponta Delgada, that brought together several people from different branches of the Government.

The conference was on the theme “Natália Correia, a Woman ahead of her time” and included speeches by Iva Matos, the Director of the Public Library and Archive of Ponta Delgada and Ângela Almeida, writer, and researcher. During the networking event, the ATHENA project was disseminated by Gisela Nascimento to the several authorities, ONGs, researchers and civil society present.

Figure 5: "Natália Correia, a Woman ahead of her time" Conference

National Scientific Conference "Video Games, Media, Communication, Entertainment"

Date: April 20th, 2023
Location: Kielce
Partner and Organiser: UJK

The Institute of Media, Journalism and Social Communication of Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce hosted the 4th edition of the National Scientific Conference "Video Games, Media, Communication, Entertainment".

The event gathered researchers from all of Poland, including Krakow, Łódź, Warsaw and Opole. It was also an opportunity to present the Athena Project. Weronika Sałek and Natalia Walkowiak from the Institute of Media, Journalism and Social Communication, members of the Athena team within UJK, presented a paper entitled "Gamers, heroines and heroes - representations of women and men in games". They were able to present the main goal of ATHENA, which is to analyse and develop new solutions for the development of the research potential of European Union scientific institutions based on a balanced policy towards gender equality in science, whilst drawing attention to the broad issue of gender equality, including in games.

Figure 6: ATHENA project dissemination through UJK members

IGUALATE Project Participatory Conferences

Date: April 25th, 2023
 Location: Gran Canaria
 Partner: ULPGC
 Organiser: IGUALATE Association

The SOMOS+ Project, aimed at the dissemination of the Higher Cycle in Promotion in Gender Equality, organized participatory conferences that took place on the island of Gran Canaria, at ULPGC.

The conferences focused on publicizing the university studies of Equality Agents and the Promotion Professionalism Certificate for effective equality between women and men, and it also went over the topics of prevention and intervention against sexist violence and the promotion of equality.

Within these conferences, the ATHENA Project was presented by several members of the ULPGC.

Figure 7: SOMOS + Participatory Conferences Poster

Conference: How to address "gender equality and inclusion of the gender dimension" in the Horizon Europe project application?"

Date: March 29th, 2023

Location: Ljubljana

Partner: JSI

Organiser: Slovenian Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation

With an audience of research institutions, researchers, policy makers, and citizens interested in the topic, the Conference "How to address gender equality and inclusion of the gender dimension in the Horizon Europe project application?" focused on topics such as the inclusiveness in research and innovation and the importance of having a Gender Equality Plan, among many others.

Alenka Guček, within a Presentation of the "Successful Horizon 2020 / Horizon Europe applicants: How did they address the gender dimension and successfully integrate it in the project?", was able to present the ATHENA Project.

Figure 8: Alenka Guček's presentation at the Conference: "How to address "gender equality and inclusion of the gender dimension" in the Horizon Europe project application?"

2.2 Webinar

Webinars were one of the alternatives found by sister projects to organize events remotely during COVID-19 restrictions. This type of event allowed an highly interactive opportunity to disseminate the ATHENA project, through a mix of presentation, answering participant questions, and discussion of the future implications of the project.

Webinar: Gender equality in European Research, Innovation and Higher Education

Date: March 10th, 2022

Location: Online

Partner: UVSK SAV

Organiser: CZELO, LINO, PoISCA and SLORD

A virtual event was organised on the topic of "Gender equality in European Research, Innovation and Higher Education", by Lithuanian, Czech, Slovak and Polish organizations. The objective of this event was to give an overview of the

latest EU gender policy developments, as well as recent developments and illustrative cases from the Czech Republic, Lithuania, Poland, and Slovakia.

In this sense, Gabriel Bianchi participated in the “Gender equality in European Research, Innovation and Higher Education” Webinar, in order to give a glimpse of the progress made by EU gender policy, through illustrative cases from the ATHENA project’s implementation in Slovakia.

Figure 9: Webinar: Gender equality in European Research, Innovation and Higher Education Banner

2.3 Symposiums

By providing an "in-depth" discussion and exchange of ideas from experts within the field of gender equality, symposiums served as an outstanding dissemination tool for the ATHENA Project, allowing its contents to be shown to several attendees interested in the matter.

Gender in Transformation Processes: Central and Southeast European Perspectives - Interdisciplinary Online-Symposium

Date: March 30th, 2022

Location: Online

Partner: UVSJ SAV

Organiser: Department of Sociology and the Centre for Inter-American Studies, both University of Graz, Austria and the Department of Sociology, University of Zadar and the Institute of Social Sciences Ivo Pilar

As part of the Elisabeth-List-Fellowship-Programme for Gender Research at the University of Graz, Austria, the interdisciplinary symposium on “Gender in

Transformation Processes: Central and Southeast European Perspectives” focused on gender in transformation processes from a Central and Southeast European perspective.

In this symposium, the ATHENA Project was disseminated by Gabriel Bianchi, Miroslava Žilinská and Barbora Holubová, through a presentation on the preliminary results of the gender audit, including challenges regarding the issue of gender auditing in research institutions.

2.4 Debates

By creating a space in which a group of experts can meet to discuss questions, brainstorm ideas, identify problems, make decisions and develop solutions, debates proved to be especially effective in publicizing ATHENA’s implementation and results.

Debate on Women in Business and Science

Date: March 8th, 2023

Location: Online

Partner: UJK

Organiser: UJK’s Academic Office for Career Development

In 2023, the International Women's Day at Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego in Kielcach was celebrated with a debate between representatives of the women’s community in business, during the event "The Women's Side of Business" which was attended by women - students, lecturers, but also men who support women's initiatives.

This initiative, held in UJK's Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences, preceded the X-jubilee edition of Business Cafes - regular, intimate meetings between business representatives and students. During this debate, the invited experts revealed their ways of overcoming fear of changes associated with running your own business.

As Ana Kaminska, ATHENA's UJK team coordinator, presented ideas for achieving gender equality to open up the research and potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe, the motivational business women who made up the panel of speakers became interested in supporting ATHENA's efforts.

International Day of Women and Girls in Science: Academic debate

Date: February 11th, 2023
Location: Online
Partner: UB
Organiser: European Centre for Social Responsibility

The International Day of Women and Girls in Science was celebrated at UJK a debate in which members of the Science Europe Governing Board spoke out in support of gender equality in the research system.

Science Europe and many of its Member Organisations, as well as other research organisations and stakeholders, defended the rights of women and girls in research.

Many Member Organisations also highlighted examples and projects of the women researchers they fund or employ, a section in which the ATHENA Project was disseminated by Corina Ilinca.

2.5 Other events

Roundtable discussions and workshops were used by ATHENA partners to receive feedback on the progress of the project's implementation, providing a platform for stakeholders to share their ideas and provide suggestions for future implementation.

Roundtable at the Opening event of the Gender Equality Days at the Faculty of Arts

Date: February 11th, 2023
Location: Online
Partner: JSI
Organiser: Faculty of Arts of the University of Ljubljana

At the 2023's opening event of the Days of Gender Equality at the Faculty of Arts of the University of Ljubljana, the theme was the experience of creating and enforcing gender equality plans in academia, and the reckoning that there is still a lot of work to be done in the Slovenian society when it comes to women's equality.

Dr. Romana Jordan, Assistant Director for EU Affairs at JSI, who coordinates the Athena Project at the Institute, Prof. Dr. Milica Antić Gaber (Faculty of Arts, UL),

Prof. Dr. Vesna Leskošek (Faculty of Social Work, UL) and Dr. Jovana Mihajlović Trbovc (ZRC SAZU) participated at the opening roundtable. They spoke about the ATHENA Project and the constraints they faced in designing gender equality plans, which included obtaining gender-disaggregated data at the organisational level, and the challenges faced by women in academia, such as gender pay gap and career progression.

Dr. Romana Jordan also spoke about the Institute's sustainable business model, which, by being sensitive to diversity, provides a supportive working environment for all.

Figure 10: Romana Jordan's participation at the Roundtable at the Opening event of the Gender Equality Days at the Faculty of Arts

Multievent of the Project O'Bias, Overcoming Gender Bias in Career Opportunities

Date: December 7th, 2022
Location: Kielce
Partner: UJK
Organiser: Education by Internet Association

“Diversity and equality in schools and universities: How to approach the Gender Equality Plan?” was the title of a presentation given by Joanna Rudawska, PhD, the Ombudswoman for Gender Equality at the Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce and member of the ATHENA project team.

The lecture served as the introduction to a discussion at a multievent organized for a related project O'Bias ([Overcoming Gender Bias in Career Opportunities project](#)) run by [Education by Internet Association](#), an ATHENA project

stakeholder. The objective of the O’Bias project is to contribute to the reduction of gender bias in labour market communication processes, particularly in the development of candidates’ job offers and resumes.

The presentation of the ATHENA project’s objectives and outputs was intended to demonstrate the need for a strategic approach at the organizational level to equality activities. Participants learned about the guidelines for preparing and monitoring Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).

It was noted that the GEP is currently only required for public institutions applying for Horizon Europe funding, but the document developed and presented by Jan Kochanowski University document can be considered a “good practice”. Participants agreed that actions on diversity and equality, stereotypes, and prejudices are effective if they are incorporated into the systematic and planned activities of an organization’s diversity strategy. It was emphasised that specific solutions should be built into existing processes and procedures in any organization, whether public or private.

The meeting was intended for employers, teachers, trainers, human resource specialists, and job seekers. Over fifteen individuals actively participated in the session, representing institutions such as the university, secondary schools, Labor Office, Vocational Training Institute, and Association of entrepreneurs. The Organisers planned an interactive game of equality bingo and a knowledge test on the subject. The conference concluded with networking.

Figure 11: Joanna Rudawska’s presentation of the ATHENA Project

Workshop in “Gender Equality, Research and Transfer at the ULPGC”

Date: October 27th, 2022
Location: Gran Canaria
Partner and Organiser: ULPGC, CE

Consulta Europa (CE)’s EU project manager, Marlene Santacruz, presented ATHENA at the Workshop “Gender Equality, Research and Transfer at the ULPGC”. The seminar was organised by the Equality Unit of the ULPGC and hosted by the Institutional Headquarters of the university.

Carmen Grau Pineda, Director of Teaching Staff, highlighted the importance of equality plans as a way to achieve effective equality in research. Carolina Mesa, Director of Equality, discussed the measures envisaged for the new plan, which recently began its implementation phase.

The seminar also included a round table with the participation of female university researchers who enriched the workshop by sharing their experiences regarding the barriers they have encountered in their academic and professional careers. In addition, they contributed with ideas and possible measures that could be carried out within the different research fields.

Figure 12: Marlene Santacruz’s presentation of the ATHENA Project

3. Lessons learnt and recommendations

From the experience of organising and participating in all the events described before project partners have gathered a series of recommendations and lessons learned that may be helpful for the next events as well as future dissemination actions of the consortium or other similar EU projects. These lessons may contribute to different aspects of planning a project intervention, such as format, content and structure, synergies, and the event promotion. This section will provide initial tips and recommendations for different aspects of the event organisation & attendance so far gathered by the consortium until M30. These recommendations will be fine-tuned in the next version of the report due at M48.

Event format

Face-to-face events are often thought to promote a greater direct interaction and engagement with stakeholders, normally through more creative and less traditional activities. However, due to Covid-19 restrictions various partners had to dismiss the original ideas that they had planned for in-person events' organisation or attendance and opt for an online format. It can be highlighted that online format proved to have advantages i.e., it was easier to attract a wider audience and it allowed for people from different locations to connect. However, some difficulties can be highlighted i.e., it was more challenging to reach and involve local stakeholders or some potential participants would cancel their participation because they were already spending too much time on online calls and working online from home. On the other hand, the online format might also affect the level of engagement with the participants. Some project partners realised that the face-to-face events has successfully facilitated the discussion and exchange of ideas and that sometimes they cannot just simply use the same structure or agenda for the online format.

From these experiences, to promote an event action, it can be concluded that first, it is important to always consider the target audience, trying to adapt the event format to their needs and availability. Another important aspect is to find the most effective way to approach a specific target audience.

Moreover, in case the event must be held online, further efforts shall be made in order to ensure interaction and that participants get involved. This is also key to get their feedback and motivate a sense of "community". The organiser must then consider engagement approaches that allow a space for debate and for participants to share their experiences. Fortunately, for online events, there are

various tools and digital platforms that can be used to make the most of the event and organise it in an efficient and effective way. Some suggestions for common and effective online activities/format are:

- **Debates:** a conversational process that brings a group of people together to share experiences and learn from each other. With this more informal format, the main objective is to connect with the stakeholders, rather than attempting to make decisions or reach consensus. For this activity, it is recommended to involve an “inspiring guest”, which might boost participation from further stakeholders.
- **Workshops:** this format aims at a more formal interaction with the stakeholders. Depending on the expected outcome, the workshop will have a specific objective i.e., to collect information, to provide a safe environment for testing and learning a method, or to reach consensus over a particular issue.
- **Webinars:** they are great for providing knowledge and building skills on a specific topic while fostering discussion and peer learning.

Besides these online tools and activities that facilitate discussion and interaction, there are also other creative and entertaining platforms that can be used to include Q&As, quizzes and polls, such as Slido, Kahoot or Mentimeter. These tools keep the event more dynamic, allowing the organisers to include more fun activities. Furthermore, these platforms are helpful to motivate that everyone gets involved, in case participants feel shy or prefer to reply anonymously. This is also useful to build a safe environment and to allow everyone to be heard.

Event structure and content

From the experience of the events held or attended so far, ATHENA partners have collected some tips regarding the structure and content of the event itself. For example, in the same way that one should bear in mind the target audience for the format (face-to-face, online or hybrid) it is also advisable to take this into consideration when deciding the timing of the event. Organisers should study the best time in the day for the target audience as well as the time of the year. For instance, some partners expressed that the academic community (including teaching staff and students) would have difficulties in attending events during certain seasons of the year because of their heavy workload and the exam sessions.

Another point to consider is to limit the scope of the event to a pre-determined number of topics so that there is time to share the project’s results but there is also space to listen to the community and to allow a co-creation process between researchers and participants. One idea suggested by CE in relation to having more time for discussion, is to share in advance the materials that will be

discussed with the participants in the event, so that participants are already familiar with the material and there would be extra time to debate during the event.

Regarding the structure of the event, the project has learnt that events are particularly successful when they manage to encourage interaction and motivate participants to engage with each other. The aim is to keep the event dynamic and interactive. Some of the activities that can be included are “icebreakers”, debates, panel discussions, testimonies from guests and “local heroes”, etc. These sessions can be combined with more workshop-like presentations, too. It is also recommended to allow space for networking among the participants, when relevant. Nevertheless, it is important to also consider the number of people we would like to involve in the event. This could depend on the aim and content of the event.

In conclusion, regarding the structure and content of the events, ATHENA partners have learned so far that it is essential to consider the specific stakeholders one wants to address when planning the event agenda. The best timing for them should be considered, along with how to approach them and the topics that they might find more relevant. The agenda should allow space for both researchers and participants to contribute, and the activities planned should stimulate interaction and exchange of ideas.

Synergies with other projects and initiatives

It shall be pointed out that ATHENA interventions organised in synergy with other conferences have been highly successful. With these synergies, not only do partners save in resources, but they also facilitated the stakeholders’ engagement, and the participation was normally higher. Partners recognise that organising their ATHENA promotional actions in synergy with other initiatives or projects helps to strengthen their relationship with these networks / institutions / associations, which could be beneficial for future collaborations. Another outcome to highlight is the collaboration between some partners from the same country / region as ULPGC and CE, to join forces and share networks/contacts for wider event impacts.

Event promotion

One of the key strategies in order to ensure participation and to reach more stakeholders, is a good promotion of the event. This was done both in the partner’s and the project’s digital channels. From their experience, partners have highlighted that it is recommendable to ensure an early promotion of the event. This will help to make sure that there are enough participants and to try other strategies in case the dissemination has not been as effective as expected.

For the promotion of the event, firstly one should make use of resources that are already available, such as the project's newsletter. Information about the event's attendance/organisation can also be posted on the project's social media channels. It is important that the promotion and dissemination is reinforced by project partners, for example, by sharing the project's posts from their institutional social media channels. The project's website is another important tool, where we can upload the agenda and details of the event to the sections "News" and "Events".

On the other hand, when organising a dissemination event, it is recommended to directly send official invitations to potential participants and share the information with sister projects, which might be interested in participating and promoting the event. Finally, it is recommended to encourage participants and other speakers to promote it within their own network.

For the promotion of local events, it is also useful to try to engage with the local media (local TV or papers). This will help specially when the aim is to involve local stakeholders. If the project intervention is held in synergy with another event, the promotion will normally be strengthened, as organisers can reach a larger audience using the same resources.

To conclude, all of these lessons learned that partners have gathered from all the different event experiences and will be taken into account for future events. These lessons can be also useful for the organisation of the project Final Conference at the end of the project and can be of help for other EU consortia.

4. Conclusions

To sum up, the present report provides a comprehensive overview of ATHENA Consortium's efforts to disseminate and communicate the project to mostly external target audiences through the organisation of and participation in online and offline events as part of the project communication & dissemination strategy. It lays out an overview of all the events and other related activities in which the project was presented, as well as report initial lessons learnt and recommendations for event management and planning. The period of reference of the deliverable, as per Grant Agreement, goes from the beginning of the project in February 2021 (M1) to June 2023 (M30).

The documented activities have been clustered according to the type of the actions (conferences, symposiums, webinars, debates). This way, the current deliverable demonstrates continuity and provides evidence necessary to the planning of the future actions of the project disseminations. The report features networking activities of the Consortium Members and all the additional actions taken to promote the project and its scope (i.e., press releases, interviews, events etc.). This is the first of two versions of the Report on participation and organisation of events (M30 and M48).

Overall, it can be pointed out that the implementation of Task 7.5 was initially constrained by the global COVID-19 pandemic that forced many ongoing EU-funded projects to readjust their activities in accordance with local/national/international restrictions. Hence, during the first year of the project (2021), ATHENA, like its sister projects, sought out alternatives to organise events remotely, through the use of online platforms and tools, whilst still gathering a substantial audience. Since May 2022, however, activities involving physical interaction and travels (i.e., face-to-face trainings, mutual learning events, project meetings, etc) were resumed, as most restrictions were lifted, in order to ensure that the ATHENA project reached its dissemination goals.

The exploitation of synergies with sister projects and other initiatives and events in order to maximise ATHENA's impact and efficiency has successfully started to be implemented and will continue during the remaining time of the project life. In particular, the ATHENA partners have been able to create synergies with other sister projects, namely SPEAR, WEGO! 3, CHANGE, Equal4Europe and GENDERACTION.

The ATHENA consortium was also very diligent in disseminating the produced work information among relevant stakeholders, in particular RPOs, including Higher Education Institutions and RFOs and also public authorities in charge of education, research and work policies. The dissemination activities that have been carried out this far have facilitated the engagement of gender organizations, policy makers, universities, institutions, research organisations, students, and the media. Countries that have been involved in the external dissemination activities include The Czech Republic, Slovakia, Romania, Japan, Denmark, Moldova, USA, France, Australia, India, Finland, Pakistan, Austria, Greece, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Israel, Malta, Croatia, Brazil, Serbia and the Netherlands.

For the next reporting period, which covers the months July 2023 to January 2025, the focus will be on further disseminating the activities of the partners, the results achieved during the Gender Equality Plans' monitoring and implementation, as well as exploit final conclusions and learnings towards the end of the project.

Next steps will be taken to maintain the overall dissemination and communication of projects activities, to maximise the impact of the outputs and conclusions of the project and raise awareness about the state of gender equality in the project organizations and countries, also to continue to present the reality of women in the context of the RPOs and RFOs.

The priority will now be on improving certain elements which need attention, as covered in Section 2 of this report. The project has achieved good results towards meeting the Key performance indicators (KPIs) for communication and dissemination previously established in ATHENA D7.1 Dissemination and Communication strategy, and the focus will now turn to surpassing them. This deliverable is the first version of the Dissemination and Communication activities. The final version will be delivered at the end of the project in M48 (January 2025).